

Ectrepesthoneura arturi sp. n. from Baltic amber (Diptera: Mycetophilidae)

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Abstract: A new species of the fungus gnats family Mycetophilidae from middle Eocene Baltic amber is described. The new species differs from previously known species of the genus mainly in the male terminalia: presence of two groups of three very long, lanceolate at the tip “megasetae”. The species’ affiliation of *Ectrepesthoneura magnifica* (Meunier) and the synonymy of *Willistoniella* Meunier with *Ectrepesthoneura* are briefly discussed.

Keywords: Eocene fossil resin, fungus gnats, new species, Sciaroidea

Introduction

There is no consensus on the systematic position of *Ectrepesthoneura* Enderlein, 1910. Traditionally, the genus has been placed in the subfamily Leiinae following Edwards (1925), but Tuomikoski (1966), Väisänen (1986), Ševčík et al. (2013), Kaspřák et al. (2018) considered that it should be placed in Gnoristinae, while Oliveira & Amorim (2021) placed it in the subfamily Tetragoneurinae.

Ectrepesthoneura has been distinguished from the closely related *Tetragoneura* Winnertz, 1846 by a combination of two venation characters: the long vein Sc ending in R and a very short-stalked or sessile posterior fork; in *Tetragoneura* vein Sc is short and ending free, and the posterior fork has a relatively long stem (Chandler, 1980).

Eighteen recent species of *Ectrepesthoneura* are known: 12 in the Palaearctic and six in the Nearctic (one of them with Holarctic distribution), and one in the Oriental Region (Bechev, unpublished database). Of the previously included species, *E. japonica* Sasakawa, 1961 and *E. yasamatsui* Sasakawa, 1961 were excluded from the genus by Chandler (1980), *E. chandleri* Caspers, 1991 was transferred to *Lusitanoneura* by Ribeiro & Candler (2007). *E.*

bucera Plassmann, 1980 synonymized with *E. ovata* Ostroverkhova, 1977 by Kjaerandsen et al. (2007) were restituted by Kjaerandsen & Soli (2020).

The described fossil species of the genus are *E. succinimontana* Blagoderov & Grimaldi, 2004 from Taimyr amber (Taimyr Peninsula, Siberia, Upper Cretaceous), *E. swolenskyi* Blagoderov & Grimaldi, 2004 from New Jersey amber (USA, Upper Cretaceous), *E. magnifica* (Meunier, 1904) and *E. mikolajczyki* Klimont & Krzeminska, 2016 from Baltic amber (middle Eocene) and *E. rottensis* Statz, 1944 from compression (Rott, Germany, Oligocene).

Material and methods

The specimen examined was found in Baltic amber collected by Artur Michalski (Wrocław) in the Baltic region (Poland). The fossil resin is of Eocene origin with an age span from the Lutetian to the Priabonian, 47.8–33.9 Ma (Grimaldi & Ross, 2017).

Habitus photographs were taken by Artur Michalski using a Canon EOS 600D digital camera mounted on a Nikon SMZ1500 microscope with a Plan Apo lens, and a CombineZM focus stacking software is used. The terminalia were photographed

by the author with a Canon EOS 750D camera fit to a compound microscope. The photographs were combined using the Helicon Focus 5 software from multiple gradually focused images. The morphological terminology follows Søli (2017). The type material is deposited in the National Museum of Natural History, Sofia, Bulgaria.

Results

Ectrepesthoneura Enderlein, 1910

Willistoniella Meunier, 1904: 74. Type species: *Willistoniella magnifica* Meunier, 1904: 74, by monotypy. Preoccupied by Mik, 1895. Synonymy: Edwards (1940).

Note: According Edwards (1940) “The correct name for *Willistoniella* Meunier is therefore *Ectrepesthoneura* Enderlein”. This synonymy is questionable because according to Meunier’s figure, the vein R4 is absent in *Willistoniella*. The type specimen of *Willistoniella* (or any other specimen of this name) is missing in the Meunier’s collection in Goettingen (Klimont & Krzeminska, 2016).

Meunieria Johannsen, 1909: 87. Replacement name for *Willistoniella* Meunier. Preoccupied by Kieffer, 1904.

Ectrepesthoneura Enderlein, 1910: 155. Type species: *Tetragoneura hirta* Winnertz, 1846: 19, by original designation.

Ectrepesthoneura arturi sp. n. (Fig. 1)

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Type material. Holotype ♂: Baltic amber inclusion preserved in 25×13×6 mm piece of amber (Fig. 1A) collected in the area that includes the villages of Mikoszewo, Jantar, Stegna and Sztutowo, Gdańsk district, Poland, leg. Artur Michalski, in National Museum of Natural History, Sofia, Bulgaria.

Preservation. The insect is completely preserved and best visible from a fronto-lateral view. Parts of the wings are hidden due to folding in the amber, The genitalia are well visible in ventral view, the dorsal view is obscured by an oblique position in the amber.

Etymology. Named in honour of Artur Michalski, the collector of the amber piece.

Diagnosis. Among the fossil species in the genus, this species differs from *E. magnifica* by presence of R4, from *E. rottensis* by costa reaching far beyond R5 (not beyond R5 in *E. rottensis*), from *E. succinimontana* by setae on scutum mostly curved backward and flagellomeres 2× longer than broad (setae curved forward and flagellomere length about equal to width in *E. succinimontana*). From *E. swolenskyi*, *E. mikolajczyki* and from all recent species, it differs in the male terminalia: presence of two groups of three very long “megasetae”, lanceolate at the tip.

Description. Male (Fig 1B). Wing length 2.8 mm. Colouration dark brown, setae and hairs pale.

Head. Three ocelli, distance of lateral one to eye margin more than twice ocellus diameter. Scape conical, pedicel short, rounded. Flagellum 14 segmented. Flagellomeres cylindrical, covered with short setae, elongated, approx. 2× longer than broad; terminal flagellomere conical.

Thorax. Mesonotum with numerous long backward curved pale setae on the periphery. Proepisternum with numerous pale setae, anteprepronotum with three long pale setae on posterior margin. Rest pleurae with only some very fine short setulae.

Wing (Fig. 1C). Hyaline, unmarked, membrane covered only with microtrichia, irregularly arranged. Costa produced beyond R4+5 to about 1/2 of distance between tips of R4+5 and M1. Sc long, ending in R. Radial cell 2× as long as wide. Ratio length of radial cell/ r-m/ stem of M-fork = 1:1.2:1.7. Base of Cu-fork very close to wing base. Setulae on wing veins not clearly visible and therefore not commented on.

Legs. Fore and mid coxae with numerous anterolateral setae, hind coxae with posterolateral setae. All femora with long, irregularly arranged bristles. Tibiae with very short bristles, irregularly arranged; hind tibia with setulae in posterodorsal area. Anteroapical depressed area of fore tibia poorly developed. Ratio fore tibia/fore tarsomeres = 4:3:1.2:1.0:0.8:0.7. Mid tibia with a slight swelling of 1/3 of its length and a slight sensory field visible. Tibial spurs formula 1:2:2.

Abdomen (Fig. 1D). Thickly clothed with long pale hairs. Two longitudinal concave folds are visible on sternites IV–VI. Terminalia rotated axially and flexed dorsally (Fig. 1D). Ventral view (Fig. 1E, F) clearly visible, but some parts cannot be definitively

Fig. 1. *Ectrepesthoneura arturi* sp. n.: A – piece with position of the insect; B – total view of holotype; C – wings; D – abdomen, lateroventral view (not in scale); E – male terminalia, ventral view; F – male terminalia, author's interpretation of ventral view. Abbreviations: bCuf = base of Cu-fork, cer = cerci; gcx = gonocoxite; igs = inner gonostyle; LW = left wing; meg = megaseta; ogs = outer gonostyle; omeg = origin of megasetae; RC = radial cell; RW = right wing; st M = stem of M-fork.

Fig. 2. A – Late Cretaceous (latest Maastrichtian, 65.5 Ma) map with localities of fossil species: 1 – *Ectrepesthoneura swolenskyi*, 2 – *E. succinimontana*. B – Late Eocene (Priabonian, 35.6 Ma) map with localities of fossil species: 3 – *E. magnifica*, *E. mikolajczyki* and *E. arturi* sp. nov; 4 – *E. rottensis*. C – Modern world map with localities of fossil species and southern known localities of recent *Ectrepesthoneura* species: 1 – *E.* sp. undescribed in Morocco, 2 – *E. gracilis* in Malta, 3 – *E. ledenikiensis* in Greece (Peloponnese), 4 – *E. hirta* in Georgia and *E. montana* in Azerbaijan, 5 – *E. ovata* in Tomsk region (Siberia) 6 – *E. bucera* in Kuznetsk Alatau (Siberia), 7 – *E. vacca* and *E. complexa* – Michigan (USA), 8 – *E. canadensis* in British Columbia (Canada) and Chukotka (NE Siberia), 9 – *E. johor* in Singapore. Maps from Scotese 2014a, b; border of arid zones according to Scotese et al. 2014.

assigned to a specific structure. Gonostyles appear to be two-branched. Outer branch relatively wide, with parallel sides. Inner branch ending with small processes provided with single setae. Two groups of three very long “megasetae”, lanceolate at the tip, but with unclear bases, probably on inside of gonocoxites. Dorsal view is obscured by an oblique position in the amber.

Female. Unknown.

Discussion

In *Ectrepesthoneura magnifica* (Meunier), described as *Willistoniella*, the vein R4 is absent (Meunier 1904, Plate VII, fig. 2). This feature is not present in any other fossil or recent species included in the genus, which makes the species' affiliation and synonymy of *Willistoniella* with *Ectrepesthoneura* questionable. Unfortunately, the type specimen of *Willistoniella* (or any other specimen of this name) is missing in the Meunier's collection in Goettingen (Klimont & Krzeminska, 2016).

The distribution of recent species of *Ectrepesthoneura*, in Holarctic and Oriental Regions (Fig. 2C), suggests a boreal origin for the genus. The localities of the fossil species (Fig. 2A–C) support this view: origin at the latest during the Upper Cretaceous in forests of the Northern Hemisphere.

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